

REPORT ON VEX/VMC BORESIGHT VECTOR CORRECTION

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Summary.

This report outlines my contribution to the analysis of the navigation for images obtained with the Venus Monitoring Camera (VMC) onboard Venus Express (VEX). The navigation of the VMC images is carried out using the SPICE kernels generated for the VEX mission, and the SPICE kernels are read using NASA's ICY routines. The navigation issues were examined both manually and automatically, using an IDL routine built for that purpose which will be described below. Only nadir and limb observations taken with the UV filter were examined in this work, discarding all the cases where the limb was not clearly visible.

Apparent problems observed during the analyses of the images were the following:

1. **Pointing errors:** when confronted the image and the coordinate grid obtained with the SPICE kernels, the match is not accurate enough in most of the cases. For this reason, in most of the images the planet's coordinate grid appears slightly shifted relative to the planet disk.
2. **Grid Size errors:** even after correcting the pointing mentioned in 1., sometimes the grid obtained with the SPICE kernels seems not to have the same size as the planet disk, being somewhat smaller in many cases and larger in others. Several cases are shown in the Appendix.

The IDL routine to test the VMC navigation.

This routine arose from the need to characterize quantitatively the navigation problems and to manage the very large VMC dataset. The testing and corresponding corrections were done in, basically 4 steps:

1. **VMC image Aperture:** along with the image, important information from the header is also extracted, including image time, saturation pixels, blemishes, corrections already applied, etc...
2. **VMC image First Navigation:** inserting the date and time from the opened image, we use the SPICE kernels to carry out the navigation, i.e., assigning a value of geographical coordinates to each pixel in the image. The way navigation is done follows the next scheme:
 - a. *VEX position from Venus is calculated.*
 - b. *Transformation matrix between Venus and VMC coordinates is obtained.*
 - c. *The VMC Boresight vector is calculated in Venus coordinates and intersection with Venus ellipsoid is inferred.*
 - d. *Intersection with Venus ellipsoid is also calculated for each viewing vector.*
 - e. *Coordinates are calculated for each viewing vector intersecting the Venus ellipsoid.*

3. **Test for Degree of Match between planet image and grid:** to check if there is a good match between the grid obtained with the SPICE kernels and the disk of the planet as observed in the image taken by the VMC ultraviolet filter, this is the procedure:
 - a. *From the grid of coordinates, we check if we have enough number of dayside limb pixels to carry out a circle fitting.*
 - b. *We binarize the grid array, separating planet from space pixel (this is done estimating a threshold value from the grid histogram). Then, a kernel is applied to keep only limb pixels.*
 - c. *When extracting the limb pixels in the image, it is necessary to exclude the limb darkening pixels. This is done convoluting the image with a gradient operator and keeping those whose gradient value is higher than a pre-defined threshold.*
 - d. *In the case of nadir observations, a circle fit is carried out for both grid and image, extracting the circle radius and centre position.*
 - e. *In the case of limb observations, the circle fit is not reliable and the correction is made by means of a cross-correlation of the binarized versions of image and grid. When the difference between the values of the maximum correlation coefficient and the second highest is less than a 10 % of the maximum, the one corresponding to the smallest shift is usually chosen.*

4. **Correction of Navigation:** As the shift necessary to correct the navigation of the images is calculated with a sub-pixel precision, the following is done to get the proper correction for the SPICE navigation:
 - a. By means of interpolation in the arrays from SPICE kernels, we get a coordinate grid with a resolution 10 times higher.
 - b. After applying to the high-resolution coordinate grid the shift necessary to correct the navigation, the coordinates for the central pixel are obtained. These coordinates will be the new Longitude and Latitude for the new VMC boresight vector.
 - c. A second navigation is carried out with the SPICE kernels, but this time a new transformation matrix is calculated for the coordinates of the VMC camera and the ones expected with the corrected boresight vector (step 4b). The pixels' viewing vectors are then rotated according to the new boresight vector and the corrected navigation grid is obtained.
 - d. To characterize the correction, two angles are used. The *amount of correction* (ϕ) is determined by the angle between the two boresight vectors, i.e., the angle between the corrected boresight vector and the former VMC Z-axis. The *direction of correction* (θ) is determined by the angle between the corrected boresight's horizontal projection and the X-axis of the former VMC X-Y frame (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Angles for Boresight vector correction.

It is also important to mention additional capabilities of the software, which can be used together with the navigation corrections:

- a) The software creates image-formatted (PNG) previsualizations of the VMC images already navigated, displaying the grids of Latitude, Longitude and Local Time.
- b) It also creates lossless-compression FITS files containing not only a detailed header with the important information about the VMC image, but also the arrays corresponding to the original image, latitudes and longitudes. The grids of Local Time, Solar Zenith Angles and Emission Angles can be generated with the Subsolar and Subspacecraft coordinates, also in the header.
- c) A log file is also created or updated after reading each image. This log file uses both the image header and SPICE data to generate, for each VMC image, information on more than 60 useful parameters. An associated excel file can be created from the log file and used to look for images attending to specific conditions of Latitude, Longitude, Local Time, Phase Angle, Distance, Spatial Resolution, Percent of Contrast for both day and nightside regions, number of pixels and grey levels, exposure time, dates, etc...

Test for VMC Navigation.

Based on the assumption that second-order corrections could still be necessary on the boresight vector belonging to the VMC camera and that this small deviation could account for the navigation problems, a first test was done using a set of VEX orbits that were exhaustively studied with former versions of the mentioned IDL software. This set was selected to allow for VMC images of different quality and observation conditions, covering orbits 29, 38, 150, 300 and 470. The results for the corrections in the boresight vector are shown in figure 2, with (2A) displaying the direction of correction and (2B) the amount of correction (quantities expressed in degrees relative to an axis):

Figure 2: Corrections for VMC boresight vector.

The circle fitting carried out by our software is fairly precise in most of the cases, though a manual filtering was done to discard to remove unsatisfactory results. Although panel (2B) shows an approximate deviation amount for the boresight of $\sim 0.1^\circ$ for different observing conditions and distances between planet and spacecraft, there is a high dispersion for the direction in the correction with no clear tendency to a fixed angle (panel 2A). Moreover, concentrations at values 0° , 45° and 90° are apparent, what could be related with the combined effect of the spatial digitization in the image and the small value for the amount of correction. Figure 3 shows an example of the expected certainty when estimating a direction when having shifts of ~ 1 pixel and ~ 11 pixels:

Figure 3: Digitization effect on the determination of direction.

From our results in orbit 300 it is also shown that an amount of about 0.1° in the boresight vector are associated to corrections shifts in the grid of less than 2 pixels in most of the cases:

Figure 4: VMC pointing correction in orbit 300

Figure 6: VMC boresight corrections for a set of high spatial resolution images.

Suggestions for future tests.

- Define a set of plausible positive and negative time delays and use this software to make a systematic comparison between the centre positions for planet disk and coordinate grid. Finding a constant deviation for a fixed time delay within the same orbit would be indicating the validity for this hypothesis combined with a second-order deviation in the boresight vector.
- Check whether the discrepancy between the geographical coordinates for the central pixel in VMC camera and other instrument (for example VIRTIS-H) is constant. A variation could provide additional clues to solving the problem.

APPENDIX A: Examples of fits in VMC images.

VMC IMAGE WITH GRID SIZE SMALLER THAN PLANET:

v0300_0030.uv2.01 [after SPICE kernels navigation]

Figure A1: VMC image in UV filter right after the custom navigation with VEX SPICE kernels. The region of discrepancy is zoomed in the left upper region of the image.

VMC IMAGES WITH GRID SIZE SMALLER THAN PLANET:

v0300_0030.uv2.01 [after only POINTING CORRECTION]

Figure A2: VMC image in UV filter after the pointing correction with the IDL software. Regions exhibiting the size discrepancies are also zoomed.

VMC IMAGES WITH GRID SIZE SMALLER THAN PLANET:

v0300_0030.uv2.01 [after POINTING + GRID_SIZE CORRECTIONS]

Figure A3: VMC image in UV filter after the pointing and grid size correction with the IDL software. Regions exhibiting the former regions of discrepancy are also zoomed.

VMC IMAGES WITH GRID SIZE HIGHER THAN PLANET:

v0300_0074.uv2.01 [after only POINTING CORRECTION]

Figure A4: VMC image in UV filter after the pointing correction with the IDL software. The size discrepancy is apparent in the image, with the grid being somewhat higher than the planet in this case.

VMC IMAGES WITH GRID SIZE HIGHER THAN PLANET:

v0300_0074.uv2.01 [after POINTING + GRID_SIZE CORRECTIONS]

Figure A5: VMC image in UV filter after the pointing and grid size correction with the IDL software. The zoomed regions are for comparison with figure (A4).

APPENDIX B: VMC High resolution/phase images.

PRODUCT_ID	PHASE_ANGLE	CENTRAL BODY DISTANCE (KM)
v0463_0030.uv2.01	52.80°	40474.120
v0465_0059.uv2.01	58.56°	46914.746
v0465_0060.uv2.01	53.06°	40473.289
v0470_0047.uv2.01	59.73°	47064.210
v0470_0048.uv2.01	59.61°	46909.115
v0470_0049.uv2.01	54.27°	40467.938
v0471_0059.uv2.01	59.89°	46907.107
v0471_0060.uv2.01	54.61°	40465.794
v0472_0040.uv2.01	61.08°	48067.413
v0472_0048.uv2.01	60.20°	46906.526
v0472_0049.uv2.01	54.97°	40465.337
v0490_0059.uv2.01	65.65°	40452.850
v0494_0065.uv2.01	73.15°	49451.596
v0494_0075.uv2.01	69.86°	42504.775
v0494_0080.uv2.01	69.70°	42170.416
v0494_0081.uv2.01	69.66°	42091.973
v0494_0082.uv2.01	69.62°	42013.368
v0494_0083.uv2.01	69.58°	41934.601
v0494_0084.uv2.01	69.54°	41855.670
v0494_0085.uv2.01	69.50°	41776.576
v0494_0086.uv2.01	69.46°	41697.318
v0494_0087.uv2.01	69.42°	41617.896
v0494_0088.uv2.01	69.38°	41538.308
v0494_0089.uv2.01	69.34°	41458.555
v0495_0090.uv2.01	70.65°	42504.553
v0495_0091.uv2.01	70.62°	42437.916
v0495_0095.uv2.01	70.49°	42170.191
v0495_0096.uv2.01	70.46°	42091.748
v0495_0097.uv2.01	70.42°	42013.143
v0495_0098.uv2.01	70.38°	41934.375
v0495_0099.uv2.01	70.34°	41855.444
v0495_0100.uv2.01	70.31°	41776.349
v0495_0101.uv2.01	70.27°	41697.09
v0495_0102.uv2.01	70.23°	41617.667
v0495_0103.uv2.01	70.19°	41538.079
v0495_0104.uv2.01	70.15°	41458.325
v0671_0020.uv2.01	63.11°	48121.733
v0671_0024.uv2.01	57.39°	40509.119
v0673_0020.uv2.01	62.54°	48119.792
v0673_0024.uv2.01	56.64°	40507.191
v0675_0020.uv2.01	62.07°	48118.468
v0675_0024.uv2.01	56.01°	40506.034
v0677_0024.uv2.01	55.49°	40503.251
v0679_0024.uv2.01	55.09°	40501.22
v0681_0024.uv2.01	54.81°	40500.160

Table B: Set of high spatial resolution VMC images with visible limb used in this study.